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Macroeconomic policies for rapid decarbonization, steady economic transition and employment creation

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Abstract

A large number of countries have by now pledged to undertake policies aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions and achieving carbon neutrality in the coming decades. However, evidence on the suitable policy package to induce an effective and orderly transition is scarce. Recent studies suggest that abrupt and aggressive climate policy may induce macroeconomic frictions. We extend a macro-financial agent-based integrated assessment model to test a variety of policy packages aimed at rapidly decarbonizing the global economy, guaranteeing macroeconomic stability, and fostering job creation. We show that carbon taxation alone is self-defeating: its role at internalizing environmental costs and triggering rapid decarbonization finds little support. However, an ensemble of industrial regulations and public subsidies coupled with a mild carbon tax is the most promising policy toolkit to support a rapid and orderly transition. Such a policy mix can be designed to have a neutral impact on public finances.

JEL codes: C63, Q40, Q50, Q54

Keywords: climate policy, transition risk, decarbonization, macroeconomic dynamics, Paris agreement, agent-based computational economics.

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24 Main

25 Large reductions of global greenhouse gas emissions are increasingly urged to mitigate the effects of uncontrolled
26 global warming on social and natural systems. Indeed, the most recent IPCC reports indicate that the impacts of a
27 2°C increase would be considerably more severe than previously estimated [41]. To cut emissions, economies must
28 reduce their carbon intensity and, given currently prevailing technologies, this implies a decisive shift away from
29 fossil-fuel energy and related physical capital. In an adverse scenario, the transition to a low-carbon economy occurs
30 either too late or abruptly, with the costs of such transformation being potentially very high [11, 61, 79]. In turns,
31 policymakers increasingly emphasize the need of balance between a rapid transition and its macroeconomic costs
32 [13, 65]. However, while there is widespread agreement about the urgency of climate action to mitigate risks from
33 uncontrolled climate change, the evidence on the suitable policy package to induce an effective and orderly transition
34 is scant [84, 65], and the excessive reliance on policy instruments characterized by low political acceptability and,
35 as you shall see, low effectiveness in redirecting investments (such as carbon pricing) brings about concerns for the
36 transition outlook [71, 73, 77]. The vast majority of decarbonization pathways assessed in reports by IPCC and
37 other key institutions such as the Network for Greening the Financial System almost exclusively consider monetary
38 instruments (mostly carbon taxes and, in few cases, subsidies) to enforce the transition. This openly contrasts
39 with the real-world use of climate policies, wherein regulations (including standards), R&D subsidies, tariffs, and
40 financial instruments play a major role [72, 90].

41 In this paper, we extend the *Dystopian Schumpeter meeting Keynes (DSK)* macro-financial integrated-assessment
42 agent-based model [49, 47, 50, 48] to study the impact of an ample set of global decarbonization policies on pro-
43 duction, employment, and macro-financial stability over the horizon 2022-2160. The DSK model simulates the
44 behaviour of an economic system composed of heterogeneous households, firms, energy plants, banks and policy-
45 makers (a government and central bank; see Figure 1). The key modeling extension we implement includes the
46 electrification of production activities in the industry sector (see Methods). Such an extension allows us to study
47 how a complex economy of heterogeneous agents calibrated on global data reacts to packages of climate policy
48 instruments attempting to decarbonize the energy and industry sectors. The model reproduces economic growth
49 and emissions consistent with a “no policy business-as-usual baseline scenario” resembling historical patterns of the
50 world economy together with a wide ensemble of macro and micro empirical regularities.

51 Climate policies are introduced to shift the socio-economic system towards a decarbonization pathway. In tune
52 with the agent-based evolutionary macroeconomic and complex system literature [26, 86] the model does not account
53 for an ex-ante imposed measure of welfare. Differently, we evaluate climate policy packages by direct inspection of
54 several indicators reflecting the containment of global warming, the macro-financial consequences of policy choices,
55 the creation of employment during the transition, and the fiscal burden of the public intervention included in each
56 policy package. The goals of our study are i) to robustly assess the trajectories of development that the global econ-
57 omy could experience under alternative climate policies, and ii) to inspect the risks and opportunities dynamically
58 created during the decarbonization [62]. The climate policy instruments we include in the analysis encompass i) dif-
59 ferent types carbon tax (either constant or increasing over time and possibly rebated to firms and households) raising
60 the fossil fuel price; ii) subsidies to incentivize green R&D or green power plants’ construction; iii) command-and-
61 control regulations imposing green standards and targets to the energy and industry sectors; iv) combinations of the
62 previous three interventions. Table 1 summarizes all instruments (see also Table 3 in the Supplementary Information
63 for details).

64 Our contribution encompasses three key aspects. First, we provide a novel perspective on the selection of climate

Figure 1: **Schematic representation of the DSK agent-based integrated assessment model and the available climate policies.** Each rectangle represents a category of agents. Heterogenous agents comprise power plants, consumption and capital good firms, banks, and households. Arrows indicate the direction of flows; solid lines represent the exchange of physical goods and services (against payment). The innovative part introduced in this paper is the use of both fossil fuel and electricity as inputs for production in the capital good sector.

65 policy instruments aimed at decarbonizing the economic system, while addressing the possible transition risks [37,
 66 85]. Second, we enhance the analysis of mitigation pathways by broadening the spectrum of policies available to
 67 instigate and sustain a green transition, with a specific focus on the role of green industrial policies [76, 51]. Third,
 68 we contribute to the evaluation of macro-financial imbalances that may arise from disorderly transitions, thereby
 69 expanding the array of macroeconomic processes observable over the short, medium, and long run in comparison to
 70 conventional NGFS scenarios [65, 66, 67].

Table 1: **Overview of the climate instruments composing the analyzed policy scenarios.** Each scenario under analysis is fully characterized by single policy instruments or a combination of them (see also Table 3 in the Supplementary Information). All policy instruments are announced and implemented in 2022 (see also Methods).

Label	Policy instrument	Description
<i>Carbon tax</i>		
Tc	Constant carbon tax	Sufficiently high tax to induce full energy transition by 2100
T2	Constant carbon tax	Sufficiently high tax to keep warming below 2°C
T2h	Constant carbon tax	As T2, with full rebate of revenues on households
T2i	Constant carbon tax	As T2, with full rebate of revenues on firms
TD2	Increasing carbon tax	Exponentially increasing tax mirroring 2°C policy in DICE model
TDh	Increasing carbon tax	As TD2, but with initial value corresponding to Tc
Tsec	Constant carbon tax	Sector-dependent carbon tax: higher for capital-good producers
<i>Green subsidies</i>		
C	Lump-sum transfer	Subsidy for the construction of green plants in the power sector
R	Lump-sum transfer	Subsidy for green R&D in the power sector
<i>Command and control</i>		
E	Mandatory regulation	Ban on fossil-fuel use in the capital good sector
B	Mandatory regulation	Ban on the construction of new fossil fuel fired power plants
<i>Policy mix (examples)</i>		
BE	Mandatory regulation	Ban on new fossil fuel fired power plants (B) and on fossil-fuel use in the capital good sector (E)
CER	Regulation and transfers	Subsidies for green plant construction (C) and green R&D (R) on ban on fossil-fuel use in the capital good sector (E)
BCER	Regulation and transfers	As CER, with also a ban on new fossil plants (B)
BCERT	Regulation, transfers and tax	As BCER, with also a constant carbon tax (Tc)

71 **Results**

72 **Carbon taxation is not suited for a smooth and rapid transition**

73 Carbon pricing is the policy solution preferred by most of economists. In particular, the vast majority of the inte-
74 grated assessment literature expresses the strength of climate policy efforts through a global price on each ton of CO₂
75 emitted, either within cost-effective mitigation pathways [75, 7] or through trajectories of the social cost of carbon
76 [33, 70]. De facto, almost all scenarios in the last report of the IPCC WGIII only provides a carbon tax schedule [42].
77 However, while the idea of carbon pricing is particularly intriguing for its simplicity, its possible implementation
78 comes with a series of issues that make it inadequate to the aim of rapidly decarbonizing an entire economy within
79 a limited time, at least if not coupled with other policy interventions [37, 2, 83, 85]. As a result, carbon pricing is
80 often disregarded by policymakers in practice [72, 83]: currently, only about 23% of global emissions are covered
81 by a carbon price [91]. This calls for a more comprehensive understanding of the merits and drawbacks associated
82 with such a policy tool.

83 Our findings show the possible problems associated with employing carbon taxes as a tool to achieve swift
84 decarbonization while maintaining macroeconomic and financial stability (see Figure 2). First, we find that the
85 minimum global carbon tax that should be applied to decarbonize the world economy by 2100 should be slightly
86 more than 2.6 times the fossil fuel price, and should grow one-for-one with inflation starting from the year 2023
87 (Figure 2, Tc scenario; see also Methods). However, such a scenario features an end-of-century temperature anomaly
88 well above 3°C, thereby calling for a much more aggressive strategy to avoid serious climate impacts [47, 9].

89 In order to keep the feasibility of the Paris Agreement, the carbon tax should increase to about 14.2 times
90 the fossil fuel price, and should still grow with inflation during the low-carbon transition (Figure 2, T2 scenario;
91 see also Methods). However, such a large and enduring policy shock substantially increases the risk of a deep
92 economic downturn characterized by unsustainable high energy prices, lowered profits and depressed investments
93 of business firms, with inevitably adverse effects on the level of economic production. The temporal profile of
94 the recession is also adverse to long-term macro-financial stability. High carbon taxes induce a significant, albeit
95 transient, spike in firms' bankruptcy rates. This surge, in turn, results in substantial volumes of non-performing
96 loans and tighter credit conditions, which exerts a constraint on credit supply and contributes to prolonged periods
97 of elevated unemployment rates. Such a marked negative hysteresis [14, 25] is further visible in GDP levels that, in
98 the T2 scenario, are about 18% lower than in the baseline in 2050 (see Figure 2, panels a, g, h, i). Scenarios T2h
99 and T2i show that rebating carbon tax revenues to households and firms, respectively, can only partially mitigate the
100 adverse effects of aggressive carbon taxation. In particular, while neither strategy can entirely shield the economy
101 from the risk of a deep downturn, providing carbon tax dividends to households is more effective than subsidizing
102 firms (see also scenario T2f in Section 3 and 6 of the Supplementary Information for an alternative redistribution of
103 carbon tax revenues to firms).

104 Finally, we consider carbon taxes increasing over time (in real terms; see Table 1 and Methods). Such a
105 scheme, which is ubiquitous in the Integrated Assessment Modelling (IAM) literature and in mitigation scenarios
106 [75, 70, 74, 42], is grounded on the assumptions that i) a benevolent social planner should start decarbonizing from
107 where it costs the least, and ii) more ambitious emission abatement actions require increasingly costly technologies.
108 Both ideas have been challenged theoretically and empirically [83, 51, 4, 89]. In our setting, a social planner does
109 not exist: we simply assume the government introduces permanent policies that firms ought to face (see Methods
110 for details). In such a decentralized out-of-equilibrium setting, gradually increasing carbon taxes (scenario TD2; see
111 Figure 3) are essentially ineffective at rapidly redirecting the growth process towards low-carbon solutions. More

112 precisely, an increasing carbon tax schedule produces visible effects only when it is sufficiently high to alter the pro-
113 cesses of technological adoption and investment in both the industry and energy sectors (see Methods and Section
114 1 in Supplementary Information). Up to such a threshold, the price of carbon does not produce meaningful impacts
115 on the system's trajectory of development. The inherent delay associated with such a policy is dangerous in terms of
116 implied emissions, long-term global warming, and transition frictions when the policy effectively hits the economy
117 (see Figure 3). An increasing carbon tax starting from a relatively high value (T_c) in 2022 combines the drawbacks
118 observed in both the T2 and TD2 scenarios, without providing additional benefits to the dynamics of the transition
119 (see Figure 2, scenario TD2h). Indeed, once the kick-starting conditions for the transition are met and green tech-
120 nologies become relatively cheaper, the path-dependent nature of technological change and the non-linear dynamics
121 of firm and plant level investments (which take place either in low or high carbon capital) make the economy in-
122 sensitive to continually escalating price-based policy measures [19, 24, 23, 50]. This result contradicts the narrative
123 suggesting that gradual changes in relative prices incentivize more and more emitters to curb their emissions leading
124 to a smooth decarbonization pathway [68, 69]. To the contrary, increasing carbon tax rates beyond the threshold
125 identified in scenario T2 fails to provide significant additional impetus to the transition, while exposing the economy
126 to elevated macro-financial imbalances.

127 Overall, our simulation results show that climate policies solely relying on carbon pricing risk to be either
128 ineffective or highly destabilizing [72, 34, 87, 71]. This supports the low economic and political attractiveness of
129 such mitigation interventions.

130 **The macroeconomic benefits of coupling green industrial policy**

131 Industrial policy - viewed at large - can be intended as the set of attempts carried out by a government to shape or
132 influence the structure and development of an economy, mostly via the generation and diffusion of new knowledge
133 and new technologies within specific industries [15, 24, 80, 35, 44, 27]. Such policies typically include instruments
134 ranging from R&D subsidies to command-and-control regulation, public procurement and tariffs. Green industrial
135 policy corresponds to the subset of those industrial policies aimed at triggering a low-carbon transition and shifting
136 economic development towards a sustainable path [76, 51]. While largely adopted in practice by governments of
137 both developed and developing countries [76, 72], green industrial policies are typically left aside in the assessment
138 of mitigation pathways. Our work fills this gap by evaluating the capability of bundles of green industrial policy
139 instruments to induce a fast decarbonization without creating macro-financial imbalances (see Figure 4).

140 Simulation results show that regulation and green subsidies (i.e., BCER and BCERT policy combinations) are
141 powerful tools to rapidly shift the economy towards low-carbon production technologies without adversely affecting
142 economic stability; to the opposite, they significantly foster employment creation (see Figure 4, panels b-h). In
143 particular, our results reveal that the success of green industrial policies hinges on adopting both command-and-
144 control regulations (i.e., B and E; see Table 1; the scenario BE in Figure 4; and Section 6 in the Supplementary
145 Information for details), which are effective in triggering a swift drop in total CO₂ emissions, mostly sustained by
146 an almost contemporaneous penetration of renewable energies in the power mix and an aggressive electrification of
147 industrial production.

148 At the opposite, the scenario CER, which removes the mandatory ban on plant construction (B) from the policy
149 bundle while including two subsidies targeted to the energy sector (one for green plant construction, C; and one for
150 green R&D, R), fails to stabilize global warming by end of century, and grossly misses the Paris agreement's targets.
151 Indeed, while the dynamics of electrification aligns closely to the BE experiment (see Figure 4, panel e), the diffusion
152 of low-carbon energy technologies lags dramatically behind: the projected share of renewable energy in the power

Figure 2: **Macroeconomic and transition dynamics induced by different carbon pricing policies.** The figure collects information for five selected scenarios across a number of indicators: a) global temperature change; b) yearly CO₂ emissions; c) electricity use of the consumption-good industry (measured as unit of electricity per unit of final good produced); d) total energy (electricity and fossil fuel) use of the capital-good industry (see Methods for details); e) share of electricity in the energy-usage mix of the capital-good industry; f) share of electricity generated through renewable energy plants; g) yearly bankruptcy likelihood of consumption-good firms; h) unemployment rate; i) GDP levels in 2050 and 2100 measured in final good units. In i), the diamond depicts the ensemble mean and the bars the ensemble distribution. The thick line depicts the ensemble mean, the shaded area shows the range between the 10th and 90th percentile.

153 mix in 2050 is around 20% in the CER scenario against 90% of the BE one. Higher reliance on carbon-intensive
 154 energy sources forces firms in the capital-good industry sector (which are subject to regulation E) to electrify produc-

Figure 3: **Macroeconomic and transition dynamics induced by increasing carbon taxes.** The figure collects information for four selected scenarios across a number of indicators: a) global temperature change; b) share of electricity in the energy-usage mix of the capital-good industry; c) share of electricity generated through renewable energy plants; d) unemployment rate. The thick line depicts the ensemble mean, the shaded area shows the range between the 10th and 90th percentile.

155 tion under a relatively higher cost of electricity, which induces a prolonged increase in bankruptcy rates with respect
 156 to the BE scenario - where the electricity price is much lower - and the no-policy no-regulation Baseline. Only when
 157 the energy transition is almost complete and the green share in the power mix reaches about 80%, financial risks in
 158 CER realign to the BE scenario and the Baseline's levels. Further, excluding the electrification regulation (E) from
 159 the climate policy mix prevents rapid emission mitigation in the industry sector, where decarbonization is histori-
 160 cally more difficult and requires the discovery and adoption of alternative production technologies [28, 39] beyond
 161 the simple substitution of power sources. As a result, all green industrial policy scenarios that miss electrification
 162 regulation fail to stabilize global warming at or below 2°C by 2100 (see Figure 5, panel a; Figure 6, panels a and b,
 163 and Section 6 in the Supplementary Information).

164 A corollary of command-and-control regulations is that they force large investments in relatively expensive green
 165 capital stocks that would not have happened without such a policy. In particular, economic growth and the constant
 166 or slightly decreasing energy use (see Figure 4, panels c and d) create a steady electricity demand that the power
 167 sector needs to satisfy through rising installments of green power plants. Financing such investments increase the
 168 financial fragility of the energy sector (with respect to a Baseline scenario), which causes additional costs to the
 169 public budget (see Methods for modelling details). Though modest - i.e., slightly more than 1% of GDP per year
 170 - the increase in the public deficit registered under the BE scenario may reduce the inter-generational desirability

Figure 4: **Macroeconomic and transition dynamics induced by different green industrial policies.** The figure collects information for five selected scenarios across a number of indicators: a) global warming; b) yearly CO2 emissions of CO2; c) electricity use of the consumption-good industry, measured as unit of electricity per unit of final good produced; d) total energy (electricity and fossil fuel) use of the capital-good industry, see Methods for details; e) share of electricity in the energy-usage mix of the capital-good industry; f) share of electricity generated through renewable energy plants; g) yearly bankruptcy likelihood of consumption-good firms; h) unemployment rate; i) GDP levels in 2050 and 2100, measured in final good units. The thick line depicts the ensemble mean, the shaded area shows the range between the 10th and 90th percentile.

171 and the political acceptability of such a policy package (see Figure 6, panel e). This problem can be mitigated by
 172 coupling regulation with green investment and R&D subsidies (scenario BCER in Figure 4), which reduce the costs
 173 associated to the penetration of renewable energy sources in the power mix and, additionally, increases the transition

174 speed of the energy sector. A more rapid transition also raises GDP levels through investments, as well as the number
175 of new jobs created (see Figure 4, panels f, h and i). Green subsidies impact on the public budget in two opposite
176 ways: on the one side, subsidies foster and de-risk investments, thus leading to smaller and more infrequent public
177 recapitalization of the energy sector (see Figure 6, panel e); on the other side, they add direct policy costs. Overall,
178 our simulations show that the two effects roughly balance out, with the net policy cost of the BCER scenario being
179 statistically indistinguishable from that of the BE scenario (Figure 6, panel e).

180 The residual cost of the green industrial policies on the public budget can be sterilized by adding a mild carbon
181 tax (T) to the BCER policy mix (see the BCERT scenario in Figure 6, panel e). Beyond collecting extra tax revenues,
182 combining all policy instruments lowers the overall size of the construction subsidies needed to support the transition
183 by making fossil-fuel technologies relatively unattractive. Further, the carbon tax increases the power sector's profit
184 margin (by increasing the wedge between the price and the inframarginal plant's costs), which cuts the average bail-
185 out costs for the electricity sector (see Methods and the Section 1 in the Supplementary Information for modeling
186 details). As a final result, the BCERT policy package is also more effective than its BCER tax-free counterpart
187 at limiting emissions, with the peak temperature falling to 1.6 degrees (see Figure 6, panel b). Incidentally, the
188 (constant) carbon tax required to obtain such outcomes corresponds to roughly 2.6 times the fossil fuel price, as in
189 the Tc scenario. Note that such a carbon tax is sufficiently mild not to create significant transition frictions to the
190 economy, contrary to scenarios purely relying on carbon pricing (see Section and Figure 6). Indeed, the carbon
191 tax slightly increases the unemployment rate in the immediate aftermath of the policy announcement, when the
192 economy reacts to higher electricity prices (see Figure 4, panel h). However, such an effect is transitory and more
193 than compensated by the increased labor demand for green plant construction in the central phase of the transition,
194 when unemployment rates considerably drop below the baseline levels (see Figure 4, panel h). In general, the
195 BCERT scenario preserves all the desirable effects induced by the green industrial policy bundle on job-creation,
196 maintenance of macro-financial stability, and inducement of a rapid decarbonization in all high-emission sectors. In
197 addition, it abates policy costs and, in the long run, it delivers the highest end-of-century global GDP level and the
198 lower temperature anomaly (see Figure 4, panel i).

199 **Overall comparison of climate policy packages across multiple dimensions**

200 Our simulations show that deep, fast, and smooth decarbonization trajectories, increasingly advocated by financial
201 regulators and international organizations [67], are associated with green industrial policy pathways combining
202 different instruments. Figure 6 summarizes the performance of several climate policy packages across six dimensions
203 reflecting (i) the speed of the decarbonization process (including the ability to reach the Paris Agreement target), (ii)
204 the transition frictions induced to the macroeconomy, and (iii) the fiscal costs inflicted to the public budget.

205 Scenarios focusing only on carbon taxation either grossly miss global warming stabilization below 2°C (Tc,
206 TD2, TDh) or generate significant harmful transition frictions (T2, T2h, T2i). A special case is the Tsec scenario,
207 which introduces a sector-specific carbon tax while requiring to keep the Paris agreement within reach (see Meth-
208 ods). By more aggressively targeting the hard-to-abate capital good industry, such scenario increases the speed of
209 electrification with respect to other carbon tax-based policies. A faster transition in the industry sector mitigates the
210 adverse effects of carbon taxation on unemployment and firms' bankruptcy rates, albeit only to a limited extent (see
211 Figure 5, panels e-h). On the positive side, all tax-based scenarios create substantial fiscal space in the government's
212 budget. We interpret this evidence as a strong case for combining different instruments.

213 Some policy combinations are significantly better than others: we find that green industrial policies are an
214 essential element to keep global warming between 1.5 and 2°C by the end of century, while fostering macroeco-

215 nomic performances. Indeed, combining command-and-control regulations and targeted subsidies to specific sectors
216 enhances employment creation and leads to higher aggregate income levels than scenarios employing only mone-
217 tary incentives (see Figures 2 and 4, panel i, and Figure 6, panel c). Further, the decarbonization dynamics under
218 green industrial policies turns out to be particularly robust to the uncertainties our model accounts for (innovation,
219 bankruptcies, and firm entry) [19, 26]. Indeed, the uncertainty bands for key transition indicators (e.g. electrification
220 of industrial processes, green energy share in power mix) are markedly lower for scenarios BCER or BCERT than
221 for Tc, T2 or TD2, and especially in the period 2030-2070, which is at the heart of the transition (see Figures 2 and
222 4).

223 Macroeconomic transition risks [79, 11] also depend the composition of climate policy packages. Aggressive
224 carbon pricing exacerbates firms' fragility in the manufacturing sector, while industrial policy mitigates it (see, for
225 example, scenarios T2, ET2 and RT2 in Figure 6, panel d), at the cost of raising risks in the energy sector. However,
226 the overall impact of such imbalances on the macroeconomy is considerably milder for green industrial policies:
227 the peak unemployment rate during the transition does not significantly exceed 5% (in contrast with ca. 15% for
228 scenario T2 and ca. 10% for Tsec), while the fiscal costs of the policies is statistically significant though contained.
229 Indeed, no scenario mixing regulation and subsidies to keep the Paris agreement within reach reports an average cost
230 of climate mitigation beyond 1.5% of GDP per year.

231 Figure 6 also shows the synergies between carbon taxation and green industrial policies. Introducing a mild
232 constant carbon tax within green industrial policy packages (BCERT scenario) neutralizes the fiscal impact of subsi-
233 dies and governments' interventions to rescue the energy sector, and further speeds up the penetration of renewable
234 energies as well as the electrification of the industry sector (see previous Section). However, such result hinges on
235 the combination of both E and B regulations (see Table 1 and Section 6 in the Supplementary Information). As
236 soon as one of the two is removed from the policy package, at least one objective fails. Scenario ET2 confirms that
237 leaving aside a command-and-control policy for the power sector (B) decelerates the growth of the green energy
238 share substantially (see Figure 6 panel a.). In the CE policy experiment, which combines a construction subsidy
239 with electricity regulation (see Table 3 in the Supplementary Information), our results show a slow green transition
240 where 50% of green electricity generation is reached only by 2070 (see Figure 2 in the Supplementary Information),
241 too late to keep the Paris agreement within reach. The reason behind such failure is that energy demand peaks in the
242 early phase of the transition (caused by expansionary phases of the business cycle) is satisfied via the the construc-
243 tion of some brown plants, which are not anticipatedly scrapped. This weakens the effectiveness of the construction
244 subsidy and delays the diffusion of green energies. Excluding the electricity regulation from a scenario combing all
245 the other green industrial policies is also detrimental: the BCR scenario minimizes the transition risks (see Figure 4,
246 panels g and h), but it grossly fails at rapid emission mitigation. Finally, the RT2 scenario RT2, which excludes all
247 regulations, proves that the often advocated bundling of R&D subsidies and aggressive carbon taxation [1] does not
248 suffice to enforce the electrification of production techniques of capital good firms and, further, does not shield the
249 economy from significant instability (see Figure 6, panels a, c, d).

250 In conclusion, our results support a policy package composed of i) a ban to fossil-fuel fired plant construction
251 (potentially with grace period or ramp-down plant), ii) electrification regulation in the industry sector, iii) green
252 subsidies reducing the financial burden of green plants installment, and iv) a mild carbon tax (constant in real
253 terms and roughly doubling the fossil fuel price). Such a policy combination transforms the trade-off between
254 decarbonization and ordered transition to sustainable economic growth in complementary objectives [85] which can
255 be simultaneously achieved.

Figure 5: **Comparison of macroeconomic and transition dynamics induced by carbon taxes and green industrial policy packages.** The figure collects information for five selected scenarios across a number of indicators: a) global warming; b) yearly CO2 emissions of CO2; c) electricity use of the consumption-good industry, measured as unit of electricity per unit of final good produced; d) total energy (electricity and fossil fuel) use of the capital-good industry, see Methods for details; e) share of electricity in the energy-usage mix of the capital-good industry; f) share of electricity generated through renewable energy plants; g) yearly bankruptcy likelihood of consumption-good firms; h) unemployment rate; i) GDP levels in 2050 and 2100, measured in final good units. The thick line depicts the ensemble mean, the shaded area shows the range between the 10th and 90th percentile.

Figure 6: Overall comparison of climate policy scenarios across a range of objectives. a) The panel summarises the outcomes of each policy scenario. In particular, it shows outcomes that are considered as “good” (green tick), “acceptable” (yellow empty square) or “bad” (red cross) with respect to indicators of a rapid, smooth (i.e. with low transition risk) and economically enhancing (i.e. accompanied by signs of economic stimulus) decarbonization. Thresholds defining colors are as follows. For peak warming: 2 and 3 degrees; for renewable energy penetration speed: year of 90% green electricity 2050 and 2075 (2050 is loosely motivated by ambitious net-zero goals assuming at least 10% negative emissions [42]); for electrification speed: year of 90% electrification for capital good sector 2050 and 2075; for peak unemployment rate: 1.2 and 2 times the baseline value; for peak bankruptcies: 1.2 and 1.4 times baseline; for policy cost: 0 and 1% of GDP. Table 4 in the Supplementary Information provides all numerical values. b) peak global warming; c) peak unemployment rate; d) peak likelihood of a consumption good firm going bankrupt; e) the fiscal cost of each climate policy package to the government (negative values indicate a surplus). In panels b)-e) thick circles denote the ensemble mean and smaller dots the 10th and 90th percentiles.

256 Discussion

257 In this paper we have extended a global agent-based integrated-assessment model rooted in complex system and
258 evolutionary economics science [49, 26, 60] to investigate the effects of climate policies for a rapid and orderly
259 decarbonization. Simulation analysis from our model helps complementing the assessment of mitigation pathways
260 typically carried out within the IAM community [75, 74, 7] by adding a macro-financial dimension and a characteri-
261 zation of transition risk (in terms of firms' default probabilities and unemployment dynamics) which is currently out
262 of the most recent sets of scenarios, including those in the IPCC AR6 database and the ones developed by institutions
263 such as the NGFS and the IEA [42, 66, 65, 40].

264 Our results suggest that green command-and-control policies are very effective in triggering and sustaining a
265 rapid decarbonization, fostering employment, while guaranteeing macro-financial stability. Their downside is that
266 they increase public spending by generating financial instability in the power sector, whose costs we assumed are
267 borne by the government [38]. Coupling regulation with subsidies for green energy plants construction and green
268 R&D and a mild carbon tax mitigates such frictions and neutralizes the adverse effects on the public budget, thereby
269 delivering a win-win policy package.

270 Command-and-control regulations are particularly effective in our setting for two reasons. First, they provide a
271 clear and certain target to each high-emitting industry, thus reducing the uncertainty of future climate policy [63, 10].
272 Second, they lead the processes of technological development and adoption towards a specific (low carbon) direction
273 without substantially altering the monetary cost of investments to be paid by business firms (contrary to carbon
274 taxation; see also Methods). As emphasized in the literature on innovation and energy transitions [78, 57, 52],
275 there is empirical and theoretical evidence showing that simple cost-internalization policies, such as carbon taxation,
276 have limited and even controversial effects on firms' behaviour, while long term emission reduction targets are a
277 key determinant of corporate innovation activities towards low carbon technologies. Technology policy therefore
278 emerges as an integral element of the policy mix, complementing climate policy.

279 Our results show the inexistence of a trade-off between a rapid transition and favorable growth outlooks [67, 5,
280 85, 59]. On the contrary, we find that the two objectives are *complementary*: the transition costs under the most
281 effective policy mix (BCERT; see Figure 6, panel a) are tiny and vanish over time, while the decarbonization of the
282 economy is characterized by relatively higher employment levels than in the baseline due to larger investments and
283 faster technological change. Indeed, policy packages including regulation and public support to low-carbon energy
284 technologies all increase the pace of green innovation and temporarily reduce unemployment with respect the no
285 policy baseline. The rapid expansion of green plants leads to more jobs in electricity plant construction. Once the
286 green transition is mostly completed, employment shifts again towards the industry sector [12], where technical
287 change occurs relatively faster than during the bulk of the transition thanks to less binding regulation. This also
288 enables relatively higher economic growth in the later stage of the transition rather than in its infancy.

289 Our simulation experiments provide alternative evidence on effective decarbonization trajectories with respect to
290 the prevailing discourse in the mitigation literature along three points. First, we find that the overall costs of policy
291 packages required to keep the Paris agreement within reach are lower than previously estimated [42]: the fiscal
292 cost of climate policy does not exceed 1.5% of GDP per year in any of the scenarios stabilizing global warming
293 below 2 degrees. Second, our results contradict the leading narrative on the desirability of gradually increasing
294 carbon pricing, which suggests to start decarbonizing with low-hanging fruits and tackle expensive measures later
295 [70]. This narrative ignores path dependency and the evolutionary nature of the process of technical change, which
296 lies at the core of the systemic transformation that a green transition requires [24, 71, 60, 56, 51]. A mild carbon
297 tax can be synergic to green industrial policy only as a source of financing for other policy measures rather than

298 as a price signal inducing system-wise transformations [83, 85, 50]. Moreover, we find that the carbon tax should
299 be sector dependent, with the most expensive-to-decarbonize industries facing a higher tax rate. This would avoid
300 other sectors being subject to excessively high costs, which either increase external financing and leverage or slow
301 down investments [88]. Further, our results support the idea that if a sector takes long to decarbonize, it should be
302 tackled without delay, even if (initially) expensive. Third, our results provide a warning on the destabilizing effects
303 of excessively aggressive carbon pricing, which drastically increases the risk of a large unemployment crises caused
304 by a surge in energy prices, large drops in investments and a rise in firm bankruptcy rates [45, 79].

305 While our analysis is robust across a variety of sensitivity and robustness checks (see Section 6 in the Sup-
306plementary Information), it can be improved along different lines which requires future research. First, we do not
307 account for climate damages, which would have made scenarios Tc, TD2, TDh, BCR, CER and Baseline extremely
308 costly for the global economy and clearly undesirable from a social perspective [49, 47, 48]. While including cli-
309mate impacts would have reasonably strengthened our results, our central focus is on policy scenarios stabilizing
310 global warming within the Paris agreement’s target and avoiding the largest share of impacts on the economy [46].
311 Second, our simulations provide robust insights into the differences between alternative trajectories of the system
312 that are induced by climate policy packages. However, they do not attempt at representing quantitative predictions.
313 Third, we do not account for behavioural changes in households and firms’ decisions which may help sustaining
314 the transition process. However, we believe such changes would cut across our ex-ante policy assessment equally
315 and leave the comparative analysis unaltered. Also, we ruled out forward looking expectations of firms, which may
316 also sustain the transition through anticipation effects. However, consolidated evidence suggests that the majority of
317 agents display a backward looking behaviour [16] aligned to our assumptions. Finally, our model does not account
318 for carbon removals. Negative emission technologies should be included in the next developments of the model.

319 **Methods**

320 **The DSK model: basics and model functioning**

321 The present paper makes use of a novel development of the Dystopian Schumpeter meeting Keynes model [DSK;
322 49, 50] to evaluate climate policy packages across several dimensions. The DSK model is an agent-based simulation
323 laboratory representing a global economy and its relationship with CO₂ emissions and changes in the mean global
324 surface temperature (see Figure 1). The model has been widely used to study the effects of climate change on the
325 macroeconomy and to help design macro-financial policies addressing climate-related risks [49, 47, 50, 48, 54]. The
326 key innovation of this study is the extension of the DSK model to jointly allow for explicit decarbonization of power
327 generation, via the penetration of renewable energy technologies in the power mix, and of industrial production, via
328 electrification of production techniques.

329 The model is composed of heterogeneous and interacting firms devoted to the production of either capital or
330 consumption goods and receiving inputs from an energy sector, a financial system and a variety of households. Firms
331 in the capital-good sector engage in a Schumpeterian competition striving to innovate to improve the technology of
332 the machine tools they sell. The Keynesian dynamics stems from the investment decision of consumption-good
333 firms that buy machines either to expand their capital stock or to replace obsolete capital goods. Anthropogenic
334 emissions arise from production of goods and, especially, energy, while there is no formal representation of land
335 use and transportation. Cumulative emission are linked to temperature increases through a single equation model
336 calibrated on recent estimates of the carbon-climate response [55]. Economic growth is driven by endogenous

337 technical change, which ameliorates the set of technologies available both to firms and energy plants. The banking
338 sector, based on [21], encompasses commercial banks that gather deposits from households/workers and provide
339 credit to firms, plus a single central bank running monetary policy and buying government bonds when needed.
340 The energy sector is composed of multiple heterogeneous plants employing either a green (low-carbon) technology
341 or a fossil-fuel based (labelled as dirty, or brown) one. Energy plants conduct R&D activities in order to improve
342 the competitiveness of the technology they master. The energy market is competitive and considers a merit-order
343 mechanism allocating generation orders to plants. The climate system is affected by the CO₂ emissions caused by
344 fossil fuels fired by electricity plants and by capital good firms. The impact of emissions on global mean surface
345 temperature is described by the simple, but physically consistent C-ROADS model [81]. We do not model climate
346 damages feeding back to the economy. However, in Section 5 of the Supplementary Information we show that
347 economic impacts of our most stringent policies are far less threatening than the damages from unmitigated climate
348 change, in line with recent impact studies [46].

349 Agent based models have been increasingly advocated in climate change economics [58, 82, 3], macroeconomics
350 [30, 18, 26] and finance [6, 32] as appropriate tools to study complex evolving systems where the interactions of
351 heterogeneous agents yield emergent properties at higher level of aggregation, while the system keeps on changing.
352 The DSK model is empirically validated [29] through stylized fact replication both at micro-economic level (firm size
353 distribution, heterogeneity in productivity, lumpy investment behaviour,...) and at macro-economic one (persistent
354 fluctuations in output, endogenous growth, emergent crises, cyclical co-movements between variables,...). A detailed
355 list of the stylized facts replicated by the model and full details about its structure and theoretical backbone are
356 available in Sections 1 and 2 of the Supplementary Information.

357 **Decarbonization in the DSK model**

358 Decarbonization requires moving the economy away from high-carbon production technologies in the power and
359 industry sectors. The power sector produces electricity on demand for all firms, using fossil fuel-fired (dirty; or
360 brown) and renewable energy (green) plants. We assume that in the electricity market there is a monopolist firm
361 which invests in novel power generation capacity and employs power plants with heterogeneous costs of production.
362 Plants with the lowest unitary generation costs are the first to be activated, in line with the existence of a merit
363 order effect. The cost structure differs between green and dirty plants. In tune with previous versions of the model
364 [49], green plants face zero generation costs but large capital costs to expand generation capacity; differently, we
365 assume overcapacity of dirty plants and, in case the monopolist needs expanding electricity generation with fossil
366 fuel technologies it only needs to bear production costs. Specifically, dirty plants burn fossil fuels (e.g. coal, oil)
367 with heterogeneous, vintage-specific technologies to generate electricity. This process entails production costs that
368 depend on i) the price of fossil fuel (exogenous and indirectly calibrated), ii) the plant productivity in generating
369 electricity from fuels, and (iii) carbon taxes, which increase the price of fossil fuels. Investment in the energy sector
370 can be associated to i) the replacement of old and obsolete plants, or ii) capacity expansion. We assume that new
371 green capacity is constructed if green plants have lower lifetime costs than their brown counterparts. Technological
372 change is endogenous in the power sector. The energy firm invest in R&D to improve the technology of green and
373 dirty plants. For green plants, this means reducing the construction costs of novel plants, while for dirty plants,
374 innovations also increase energy efficiency and reduce carbon emissions. To reflect the Knightian uncertainty af-
375 fecting technological change, the outcomes of the search process for innovations is genuinely stochastic, with the
376 probability to successfully innovate increasing in the R&D investment.

377 In the industry sector, the unit cost of production of both capital- and consumption-good firms depends on

378 the price of inputs and their productivity. While machine construction requires labour, electricity and fossil-fuel,
379 consumption-good firms need labor, machine-tools and electricity. Such a difference captures the diverse use of
380 fossil-fuels across sectors of economic activity, with up-stream processes such as cement, steel or chemicals pro-
381 duction disproportionately employing fossil-fuels with respect to down-stream industries. Firms in the capital-good
382 industry adaptively attempt to increase market shares and profits by improving their machines and production tech-
383 niques via costly innovation and imitation processes. In particular, firms invest a fraction of their past sales in R&D
384 to discover a new technology or to imitate those of their competitors. As explained in [22], both innovation and
385 imitation are modeled as two-step processes. The first step captures the stochastic nature of technical change and
386 determines whether a firm successfully innovates or imitates. This is formalized in the model through a draw from
387 a Bernoulli distribution, where the (real) amount invested in R&D, that is, ultimately, number of people devoted to
388 research, affects the likelihood of success. The second step determines the size of the technological advance. Each
389 technology is defined by a set of technical coefficients representing labour productivities and the efficiency in the
390 use of energy inputs. In particular $A_{i,\tau}^L$, $B_{i,\tau}^F$ and $B_{i,\tau}^E$ represent the productivity of labour, fossil fuel and electricity
391 of firm i in the capital-good industry, while $\tilde{A}_{j,\tau}^L$ and $\tilde{B}_{i,\tau}^E$ are the productivities of labour and electricity of firm j
392 in the consumption-good industry, when employing the machine developed by firm i for production.

393 If the first step of the innovation process is successful, capital-good firms stochastically discover (through inno-
394 vation) a novel technology characterized by a different use of labour, electricity and fossil-fuel (i.e. a new set of A ,
395 \tilde{A} , B^E , \tilde{B}^E and B^F). Let us first consider how innovation affects labour productivity. The coefficients of labour
396 productivities associated with the novel technologies are $A_{i,in}^L = A_{i,\tau}^L(1 + x_i^L)$ and $\tilde{A}_{j,in}^L = \tilde{A}_{j,\tau}^L(1 + \tilde{x}_j^L)$, where x_i^L
397 and \tilde{x}_j^L are random draws from a Beta distribution with positive mean (see Supplementary Information for details).
398 Note that the notional possibilities of technological advance — i.e. technological opportunities — are captured by
399 the support of the Beta distribution and by its shape. Similarly, the productivity of electricity for consumption good
400 firms when an innovation occurs can be written as: $\tilde{B}_{j,in}^E = \tilde{B}_{j,\tau}^E(1 + \tilde{x}_j^E)$, with \tilde{x}_j^E being a draw from a Beta
401 distribution. In the capital good industry, instead, the productivity of electricity and fossil fuel use are determined
402 adapting the approach of Nelson and Winter (1982) [64, chapter 7], which reflects the substitutability of the two en-
403 ergy inputs within the capital good sector. Indeed, in our model, the decarbonization of the industry sector happens
404 via electrification, which takes place through the development of technologies substituting fossil fuel for electricity
405 as energy inputs. More specifically, let q , E and F be the level of output (in terms of capital goods) and the stock of
406 the two energy inputs required for production of q . We define input coefficients as the inverse of the productivity of
407 fossil fuel and electricity:

$$b_{i,\tau}^F = \frac{1}{B_{i,\tau}^{FE}} = \frac{F_{i,\tau}}{q} \quad (1)$$

$$b_{i,\tau}^E = \frac{1}{B_{i,\tau}^{EE}} = \frac{E_{i,\tau}}{q}. \quad (2)$$

408 We model the search of novel of techniques as a process of discrete changes of b^E and b^F . Each of such change rep-
409 resents an innovation. In a 2-dimensional plane (with axes b^F and b^E), the set of available techniques is determined
410 by:

- 411 • the ratio of input coefficients: $U_{i,\tau} = \frac{b_{i,\tau}^E}{b_{i,\tau}^F}$ and,
- 412 • the sum of input coefficients: $V_{i,\tau} = b_{i,\tau}^F + b_{i,\tau}^E$.

413 Hence, $U_{i,\tau}$ indicates the relative proportions of electricity and fuel that are needed to build a machine of vintage τ ,
 414 while $V_{i,\tau}$ indicates the total amount of energy inputs. When an innovation occurs, a new (U, V) pair is discovered:
 415 $U_{i,in} = U_{i,\tau}(1 - x_i^U)$ and $V_{i,in} = V_{i,\tau}(1 - x_i^V)$, with x_i^U and x_i^V being random draws from a Beta distribution with
 416 positive mean. If $U_{i,inn} < U_{i,\tau}$ the novel technology uses more electricity and less fossil fuel for the production of
 417 each unit produced. If $V_{i,inn} < V_{i,\tau}$ the novel technology is more efficient than the incumbent one.

418 Finally, we need to specify a decision rule for the adoption of a novel technology. In tune with previous versions
 419 of the model [22, 49, 47], a capital good firm i evaluates different technologies and machines to produce taking into
 420 account their selling price and their “quality”. In particular, it minimizes the following quantity: $p_i + b_{cg}\tilde{c}$, where
 421 p_i is the price at which the machine is sold by firm i (which is a markup over production costs of the machine; see
 422 Section 1 of the Supplementary Information), \tilde{c} is the unitary cost of production of consumption good and b_{cg}
 423 is strictly positive payback parameter indicating the financial duration of the investment in a capital good. [22, 20].

424 Calibration and simulation settings

425 The model does not allow for analytical, closed-form solutions. This stems from the non-linearities that characterize
 426 agents’ decision rules and their interaction patterns, and forces to run computer simulations to analyze the properties
 427 of the stochastic processes governing the co-evolution of micro- and macro-variables [30, 29]. We therefore perform
 428 Monte-Carlo analyses to wash away across-simulation variability and present results as averages over 50 model runs,
 429 as standard in the literature, endowed with uncertainty bands showing the 10th and 90th percentile.

430 The DSK model is calibrated to a baseline scenario characterized by high economic growth, constant economic
 431 volatility, stationary sustained energy demand, and soaring emission concentrations and temperature anomalies mir-
 432 roring historical global dynamics in the period 1980-2019 (see Section 2 in the Supplementary Information for
 433 details). We consider such scenario as representative of the trajectory that the global economy would have taken
 434 if no other climate policy had been introduced beyond those announced and implemented by 2019 and if all deter-
 435 minants of socio-economic activities remained consistent with those observed in the period 1980-2019. In terms
 436 of emissions, GDP and temperature dynamics, this scenario can be considered in between Shared Socio Economic
 437 Pathway (SSP) 5- Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) 8.5 and SSP3-RCP7.0, which are the two most used
 438 references for business-as-usual. As a consequence, any climate policy that we test should be read in deviation from
 439 those embedded in the baseline dynamics. We voluntarily left the COVID-19 pandemic period aside not to bias the
 440 calibration to rare and extraordinary global economic dynamics.

441 Climate policy implementation

442 All the climate policy scenarios feature the same initial conditions up to year 2021 (see Table 1 above and Table 3 in
 443 the Supplementary Information). The climate policy instruments included in each scenario are implemented in year
 444 2022 and kept in place until the end of the simulation period, which goes from 2000 to 2160. The simulation period
 445 extends beyond 2100 to robustly control for the effective stabilization of global warming after end of century.

446 *Carbon taxes.* Carbon taxation imposes a wedge between the fossil fuel price (pf_t) charged on (non-modelled)
 447 international markets and the cost sustained in the power and capital good sectors to use each unit of fossil fuel for
 448 production. Hence, the unitary carbon tax at time t can be written as $T_t = X_t pf_t$, where X_t indicates the magnitude
 449 of the carbon tax. This implementation of the carbon tax is intuitive, transparent and aligned to part of the literature
 450 [1, 50, 53, 59]; further, it is convenient to the structure of the DSK model, which does not include an extraction
 451 sector. Carbon taxation immediately increase both the generation costs of electricity and the production costs of

452 capital goods. In turn, this affects production and investments choices in the power and manufacturing sectors First,
453 as long as dirty plants are used for electricity generation, the carbon tax increases the electricity price. Second,
454 carbon taxation increases proportionally the lifetime costs of using dirty plants, which discourage investments in
455 fossil fuel capital stock. In particular, the power sector expands its stock of green plants if the following payback
456 rule is satisfied $IC_{ge} \leq b_e \cdot c_{de}$, where IC is fixed costs of constructing a green plant, b_e is a payback parameter
457 indicating the financial duration of the investment in a power plant and c_{de} is the unitary cost of electricity generation
458 with the most recent vintage of fossil fuel fired plant [49, 50, see also Section 1 in the Supplementary Information].
459 In turn, the unitary costs of electricity generation with the most efficient brown plant τ^* are: $c_{de,t} = (pf_t + T_t)/A_{de,t}^{\tau^*}$,
460 with $A_{de,t}$ being the thermal efficiency of vintage τ^* at time t [49]. In the capital good sector, carbon taxes alter
461 the production costs of machines: $c_{i,\tau} = w/A_{i,\tau}^L + pe_t/B_{i,\tau}^{EE} + (pf_t + T_t)/B_{i,\tau}^{FE}$, where w is the wage, A^L , B^{EE}
462 and B^{EF} are the productivities of labor, electricity and fossil fuel, pe is the price of electricity and pf the price of
463 fossil fuel. Increasing such costs has an effect on the adoption of new machine tools discovered through technical
464 change. Indeed, as anticipated above, a capital good firm i selects the technology to use according following the
465 rule: [31, 22]: $\min[p_i^h + b_{cg}c^h]$, with $h = \{\tau, in, im\}$ indicating the incumbent technology (τ), the newly discovered
466 technology (if any) through innovation (in) and the newly imitated (if any) technology (im). Almost all scenarios
467 tested in this paper consider a uniform carbon tax for the whole economy. Differently, the Tsec scenario employs
468 two levels of X_t , one for the power sector and a higher one for the hard-to-abate capital good sector.

469 *Subsidies.* Subsidies are modelled as lump sum transfers from the government to the energy sector to incentivize
470 and help financing the decarbonization process. We consider two types of subsidies. The first one (labelled as R)
471 supports green R&D in the power sector to support green innovation in renewable energy technologies. The second
472 subsidy (labelled as C) fosters investments in green energy plants by providing a payment S for every plant built.
473 The payment is made upfront, in the same period the plant is constructed. Hence, the power sector faces a lower cost
474 of the investment IC_{ge} . Beyond such direct financial effect increasing the financial resilience of the energy sector,
475 the C subsidy affects the choice between brown and green power plants described above, thus directing technological
476 change.

477 *Regulation.* Regulation comprises two command-and-control interventions: a ban on the construction of new
478 fossil fuel fired power plants (B), and a mandatory electrification of capital good production (E). Both regulations
479 are characterized by two elements: an imperative to avoid the use fossil fuels (command) and a time period after
480 which compliance with the new regulatory standard is enforced (control). We assume that regulation is credible
481 and enforceable: since the announcement of the policy all agents in the economy know that that the policy will be
482 enforced after the grace period, that is, the period between the announcement and the control. Real world examples
483 of such regulations are the standards of the Environmental Protection Agency in the US, which applies a “rules and
484 deterrence” approach [36], or the Montreal protocol through its implementation committee [8]. If a private business
485 does not to comply with the regulation after the grace period, we assume that it is monitored and has to exit the market
486 due to the imposition of a sufficiently high fine. There is no possibility to lobby [43]. The other key assumption
487 concerns the behavioural reactions to the announcement of the regulation. In the case of the B scenario, we assume
488 that the electricity firm starts expanding the stock of green power plants by investing its liquidity in new capacity (up
489 to the maximum capacity expansion, which is calibrated to a maximum growth rate of 20% per year [17]; see next
490 subsection and Section 6 of Supplementary Information for robustness). In the case of the E scenario, capital good
491 firms constrain their technological adoption decisions to introduce only those technologies that substitute fossil fuel
492 use with electricity. Note that this does not guarantee firms to fully electrify their production, as they are still subject
493 to the fundamental uncertainty of the process of technical change, which they cannot hedge against. In this sense,

494 they are maximally uncertainty averse: as soon as they can make a step towards accomplishing the regulation, they
 495 make it.

496 **Policy settings: details**

497 To define the exact values characterizing the policies studied in this paper, we first performed an extensive scenario
 498 exploration through the model calibrated on historical data. We summarize the features of each scenario reported
 499 in Table 1 below. Scenarios discussed in this work should be seen as representative of robust patterns and model's
 500 behaviours. Sensitivity analysis is shown in Section 6 of the Supplementary Information.

501 *Constant carbon tax ($T_c, T_2, T_2h, T_2i, T_{sec}$).* For this group of scenarios, the carbon tax is initialized in 2021 and
 502 it grows with inflation. The critical tax value X_c (for experiment T_c) is determined by testing tax values in intervals
 503 of $0.1pf$; the value $X_{c,2021} = 2.6pf_{2021}$ (i.e. adding 260% to the fuel price level implied by the model for year 2021)
 504 is the lowest for which a green transition takes place for all Monte Carlo runs; hence, it used as the critical value.
 505 The tax value needed to stay below 2 degrees until 2160 (experiment T_2) was determined in the same way as X_c and
 506 it is equal to $X_2 = 14.2pf_{2021}$. The carbon tax in T_2h corresponds to that in T_2 , but the tax revenues are paid out to
 507 households, who will spend any extra income on consumption. Similarly, scenario T_2i assumes the same carbon tax
 508 profile of T_2 , though with full rebate on firms as innovation (R&D) subsidies. See the Supplementary Information
 509 for scenario T_2f featuring rebates on consumption good firms. Finally, in the sector-dependent carbon tax scenario
 510 (T_{sec}), the carbon tax is 3 times as high in the capital good sector than in the electricity sector: $X_{cap} = 3X_{elec}$,
 511 where X_{elec} is chosen high enough to stay below 2 degrees warming, which yields $X_{elec,2021} = 9.1pf_{2021}$.

512 *Increasing carbon tax (TD_2, TD_h).* We consider an increasing carbon tax akin to that employed in the DICE
 513 model [70]. In order to do so, we first run the DICE model, we extract its optimal carbon tax (i.e. the marginal
 514 abatement cost), and we finally fit the result into an exponential function:

$$X(t) = X_0 \exp[\alpha(t - t_0)],$$

515 where X_0 is chosen such that in time $t_0 = 2021$, the tax raises the fuel price by the same factor in both the DICE and
 516 the DSK models (see Sections 1 and 5 of the Supplementary Information for details). Two setups of the DICE 2017
 517 model [70] were considered: i) unconstrained optimization (TD_{opt}), yielding a peak warming of 2.7 degrees above
 518 pre-industrial; optimization under the constraint that the global warming must be stabilized below 2 degrees by 2100
 519 (TD_2). In addition, a stronger policy is designed (TD_h), based on TD_2 but with X_0 increased to the critical tax value
 520 X_c . The first setup is used only to compare the size of the tax that DICE obtains with no constraints with the other
 521 scenarios. Indeed, since it misses, almost by design, the target of the Paris agreement, TD_{opt} is not investigated
 522 further through the DSK model. Our exercises yield the following. TD_{opt} : $X_0 = 0.77pf_{2021}$, $\alpha = 2.63\%/year$;
 523 TD_2 : $X_0 = 1.02pf_{2021}$, $\alpha = 4.20\%/year$; TD_h : $X_0 = 2.6pf_{2021}$, $\alpha = 4.20\%/year$.

524 *Green Research and Development subsidy (R).* The government provides the electricity sector with a subsidy
 525 $R_{g,subs} = 0.5(R_g + R_b)$, i.e. half as high as the total (green + brown) R&D expenditure of the electricity sector, to
 526 be spent on R&D for green plants. See Section 6 in the Supplementary Information for sensitivity analysis.

527 *Green Construction Subsidy (C).* The construction subsidy starts in 2021 and provide to the electricity sector a
 528 payment S for every green plant built. The size of the subsidy is $S = \max\{IC_{ge} - \gamma_{subs}c_{de}, 0\}$ with $\gamma_{subs} = \frac{1}{3}$,
 529 so the subsidy reduces the lifetime cost of green plants to 1/3 of that of brown plants, but cannot become negative.
 530 The subsidy is paid until $IC_{ge} < \frac{2}{3}c_{de}$ (i.e. the nominal lifetime cost of green plants is below 2/3 the lifetime cost
 531 of brown plants). By this time, green plants are well established, which typically means a significant green stock

532 has been built and rapid expansion ceases to be a constraint. See Section 6 in the Supplementary Information for
533 sensitivity analysis.

534 *Brown plant construction Ban (B)*: The ban is enforced from 2041 and it is announced by the government in
535 2021. After 2041, no more brown plants can be built, but the existing ones can still be used. Even if in 2021-
536 2040, brown plants may still be built, the electricity firm prepares to the ban by investing in green R&D only, and by
537 precariously building green plants to increase its stock up to its investment capacity. Note that a stock of green plants
538 insufficient to satisfy the electricity demand in 2041 would trigger a green investment surge, potentially leading to
539 bankruptcy of the electricity firm. In case of potential insolvency, the electricity firm is rescued by the government,
540 which absorbs losses and recapitalizes the electricity firms to average baseline levels. We find that a grace period
541 of 20 years is sufficient, on average, to spur the penetration of renewable energy. See Section 6 and Figure 3 in the
542 Supplementary Information for details and sensitivity analysis.

543 *Electrification regulation (E)*. The electrification regulation is implemented on capital good firms through the
544 fine $F = F_0(1 - F_{el})$ where $0 \leq F_{el} \leq 1$ is the share of electricity in the total energy inputs used by the firm,
545 and F_0 is a constant sufficiently high to make non-compliance prohibitively expensive (i.e. all capital good firms
546 electrify). Intuitively, the fine is strictly decreasing in F_{el} . A varying F_{el} across firms is used to capture a fine propor-
547 tional to the extent by which the standard imposed by the regulation is missed. The fine is enforced from 2051 but
548 announced in 2031. The 20 years grace period is sufficient to simulate near-complete electrification before enforce-
549 ment. Robustness analysis to alternative lengths of the grace period can be found in Section 6 of the Supplementary
550 Information.

551 *Composite policies*. Unless specified otherwise, composite policies are simply combinations of the above mea-
552 sures. Table 1 provides examples while the full list is available in Table 3 of the Supplementary Information. In
553 policy package BCERT (ban of brown plants + construction subsidies + electrification regulation + R&D subsidies
554 + carbon tax; see Table 1 for details) the carbon tax mirrors the one of scenario Tc.

555 **Data availability**

556 The model code and the model's settings will be made publicly available in a dedicated page on GitHub upon
557 publication of a peer-reviewed version of the paper. For reviewers, a link to the full code of the model and the
558 analysis in this study is provided in the cover letter.

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